

Developing ODS high-temperature alloys tailored for AM

Activity Summary

The project components of interest, heat exchangers and gas burner heads, experience harsh and fluctuating operating conditions, and consequently, suffer from metal dusting, high temperature corrosion and creep (operating conditions defined by project partner Linde). Three commercial alloys with the potential to meet these tough application requirements have been produced and provided as powders for additive manufacturing (AM): Fe-based AM100 from Kanthal, Ni-based 699XA from VDM Metals, and NiCu-based Monel 400 from KME. Project partners have developed laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) process parameters for all three alloys with bulk densities greater than 99.95%. Using these LPBF parameters, various specimens for mechanical, corrosion and thermophysical testing are under production for distribution to the testing partners. The powder characterization results and the mechanical and corrosion properties of these AM-built alloys will serve as references for all future material developments in this project which will incorporate oxide dispersion strengthening (ODS) into all three alloy families.

In parallel, the material simulation experts in the team have been investigating the possibilities for ODS additions. These simulation results will direct the experimental investigations for ODS modification of the powder alloys. Initial experiments within the three modification concepts of freeze granulation, mechanical alloying and internal oxidation/nitridation, have been carried out and more detailed investigations are planned.

Figure 1. Top right: modelling of creep contour plots and chemistry maps; **top left:** powder of AM100; **bottom left:** AM process optimization; **bottom center:** density analysis; **bottom right:** production of specimens for mechanical and corrosion testing.

General Assembly Meeting

The first general assembly of the topAM consortium was October 14-15, 2021 in Aachen, Germany. During the meeting the following members of the IAB were present: Dr. Astrid Rota (EOS GmbH), Dr. Adrian Ruskamp (Georgsmarienhütte Holding GmbH), and Dr. Florian Eibl (Aconity 3D GmbH). The Industrial Advisory Board (IAB) is a group of internationally renowned experts assembled to provide guidance and consultation, to support the topAM consortium at the leading edge of scientific developments.

In addition to vital information sharing, project planning and discussion, invited speakers from a US-Department of Energy-funded project, "Microstructure optimization and novel processing development of ODS steels for fusion environments (MONDO-FE)," on AM of Fe-ODS alloys for nuclear applications shared their latest results. The following discussions showed how the two projects could benefit from future information sharing and potential collaboration while broadening the impact of both.

